

CULTURAL SENSITIVITY AND CREATIVITY: BALANCING GLOBAL TRENDS AND LOCAL VALUES IN ADVERTISING PRACTICES IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This study examines the opinions of professionals regarding the significance of cultural relevance for advertisements to succeed in Pakistan. "Elite interviews" with Pakistani brand managers, creative directors, and advertising experts served as the foundation for this qualitative study. Interviewees provided insights into a wide range of issues that affect the efficacy of ads, from creative and technical aspects to cultural, ethical, and religious elements. Advertising executives strongly emphasize consumer behavior analysis, cultural studies, and moral issues. They also stress the importance of avoiding divisive subjects and setting a good example. Notwithstanding these observations, advertisements originating from multinational companies (MNCs) typically have a generic quality and lack cultural relevance. Pakistan's advertising professionals believe a well-rounded approach includes customer behavior information, cultural awareness, ethics, and innovation. Designed in collaboration with academics and professionals in advertising and marketing, the protocol featured free-form questions to promote guided reflection. The findings highlight the need to fund advertising education programs, conduct research on consumers and cultures, and develop expertise in content development. In addition to addressing issues like incompetent leadership and a lack of funding, Pakistani advertising techniques place a higher value on collaboration and originality.

INTRODUCTION

To engage audiences, advertisers must understand cultural norms, attitudes, and preferences (Friedman, 2017; Victor, 2017). Advertisements use these cultural norms to tell customer-friendly stories. People's cultural backgrounds strongly influence advertising perceptions and responses. Zhang and Gelb (1996) and Kadir and Al-Aidaros (2015) found that culturally appropriate ads are better appreciated. Offending religious or cultural sensibilities in advertisements can lead to defamation. Cultural

sensitivity is crucial to building relationships, thus advertisers must avoid violating their target audience's creative standards (Johnson, 1998). Marketing adaptation helps successful companies overcome cultural barriers (Gitman, 2018; Uzair, 2012). The vagueness of "culture" confuses this link. Despite identical criteria, Deresky (2003) and Cateora, Gilly, and Graham (2011) stress that cultural variances in behaviour arise from value systems. Schwartz and Sagiv (1995) say cultural values are built on tangible

principles, unlike individual values. Also, relatable and intelligible ads are more likely to be clicked.

Purpose statement

This research examines client-agency interactions and tech-savvy advertising strategies in Pakistan, taking cultural and socioeconomic shifts into account. It fills a gap in knowing how cultural norms affect consumer advertising by identifying Pakistani variables that boost its efficacy. Cross-cultural communication in digital advertising targeting tech-savvy Pakistanis is examined using qualitative approaches, integrating advertising, communication, culture, and strategic brand management. Interviews with advertising specialists and commercial analysis will reveal this phenomenon's major components.

Advertising influences brand perceptions and affinity among Pakistani consumers, impacted by societal conventions, the digital landscape, and tech-savvy audiences. Pakistan's young only respond to a few culturally relevant ads. Advertising must balance commercial and social ideals to work. The study examines three main questions: how Pakistan's cultural and religious context affects ad originality and likability; how advertising agencies and clients interact on culture and brand strategy; and how multinational companies (MNCs) affect cultural awareness and ethical advertising in Pakistan.

Literature Review

Understanding cultural compatibility, societal attitudes, and consumer behavior is critical to Pakistani advertising. These factors strongly influence audience loyalty, according to Strawli (2016). According to Li & Lin (2007) and Bin Said et al. (2017), Pakistani consumers may respond better to rational and accurate communication. Instead of identical translations, which may alienate consumers, Zatar (2015) suggests adapting advertising messaging to local cultural norms. Advertising must also be culturally sensitive to reach Islamic civilizations (Mostafa, 2011; Purnama and Safira, 2017). Additionally, Cui et al. (2012) emphasizes that culturally incongruent advertising that contradicts core values may be harmful. Thus, advertisers must adapt to changing social norms to create culturally relevant and engaging ads.

Comprehending Cultural Nuances in Pakistani Advertising:

Cultural influences from both the West and Islam have created a vibrant and ever-changing landscape in Pakistan (Sohail, 2023; Paracha, 2015). Changes in societal norms brought about by Western influence have prompted Pakistanis to reevaluate their cultural identity while also fueling debates inside the country on the extent and rate of this transformation. Cultural values have been altered, and society has been split as a result of Western media.

Advertising using dance, which is seen differently by various Islamic groups, is something that many Pakistani consumers find objectionable due to Islamic beliefs (Raouf et al., 2020; Faruqi, 1978). Public displays of love are traditionally taboo, although this is starting to change as a result of more exposure to media and education. Commercials are more likely to be well-received if they reflect local values and customs (Peebles & Ryan, 1984). Wells (1980) argues that cultural factors, not product attributes, determine how people respond to ads. According to Abbasi et al. (2011), Muslims are more likely to reject ads that contain sexually explicit material or otherwise go against their religious values.

To effectively advertise in Pakistan, one must grasp the delicate balancing act of cultural sensitivity and audience engagement. Ethical, religious, and cultural factors impact the appeal of advertisements and the perception of brands; future research should investigate consumer behavior, especially among tech-savvy youth.

The Challenge of Culturally Sensitive Advertising

Social class, geography, habits, ethics, culture, and religion affect attitudes towards advertising (Emerson, 2004). Pakistani advertising must combine cultural sensitivity and financial efficacy due to globalisation and digital communication (Amna et al., 2022). Advertising that matches national culture is more likely to be accepted, especially when it addresses sensitive cultural norms (Saima, 2022). Local consumer messaging views are crucial for global brands (Oded et al., 2020).

Though powerful, Rice (1999) warns that sensitive commercials may offend. According to Waller, Fam, and Erdogan (2005), "unmentionable" or "socially sensitive" products may upset, disgust, or turn people

off. Such products need good marketing in Pakistan due of the population's sensitivity. Alcohol, contraception, cigarettes, and political ads are controversial (Wilson & West, 1981). Their perceived immorality may lead to moral issues and rejection (Rehman & Brooks, 1987). Religious and gender stereotypes influence public judgement on inappropriate commercial advertising (Farah & Elsamad, 2014). Advertisements that violate religious convictions are allowed in the Middle East but not in Malaysia (Waller & Fam, 2000). Thus, advertising ethics matter most.

Advertising can offend in content or appearance (Barnes & Dotson, 1990). The commercial and brand may appeal to a viewer who likes the graphics but not the content (Homer, 1990). This means one marketing aspect might greatly affect client impression.

The Power of Storytelling in Advertising

Advertising storytelling may boost brand-customer interactions in Pakistan, where cultural narratives and emotional connections greatly influence consumer behaviour (Coker et al., 2021; Amangeldiyeva, 2022; Belova, 2021). Pakistani advertisers may establish brand loyalty and authenticity by sharing meaningful stories (Sousa, 2021).

Consumers like stories about products in everyday contexts (Adaval & Wyer, 1998). Storytelling ads generate emotion with fictitious stories and characters (Brooks, 1992; Lakoff, 2008). Dikčius et al. (2023) stress the need of avoiding cultural insensitivity and sexism in comedy. Effective advertising creates client emotions through narrative (Holbrook & Batra, 1987; Saenger et al., 2013).

Stories in public service advertisements inspire emotions and change conduct (Murphy et al., 2013; Shen & Li, 2015). In Pakistan, advertising may develop culturally sensitive stories that attract viewers despite religious bans on emotional appeals, Arenas-Osorio (2020) reports. Child storytelling is improved by language, festivals, religion, and attire (Sharma & B).

Brand likeability

Despite information saturation, modern advertising must attract customers' attention. Likeability is important because appealing ads evoke positive

feelings during the "scanning phase" of information processing, according to Biel (1990). Liked content disturbs surfing, unlike inconspicuous ads. Mortimer and Lloyd (2010) found a quadratic relationship between likeability and message clarity, suggesting that while clear messaging may work, more complex advertising may have a greater impact as simple ads diminish likeability. Culturally relevant ads are more likely to catch attention than unfamiliar ones, say Zhou and Belk (2004).

Advertising works when people comprehend it, not simply when they see it. Positive emotions boost brand perception and message comprehension, according to Biel (1990). Smit et al. (2006) link an ad's intellectual and emotional elements to its likeability, whereas Bairrada, Coelho, and Lizanets (2019) claim visually appealing and emotionally engaging ads boost brand impressions. A favourable first impression increases brand loyalty and sales, according to Bairrada et al. (2019). This "likeable" advertising aims to promote self-esteem, improve message reception, and lessen information overload.

Cross-cultural advertising reactions are explained by schema theory. Psychological schemas help people understand new information using past knowledge (Fiske & Linville, 1980). Schemas incorporate population biases (Hamilton, 1979; Ashmore & Boca, 1981). Childhood and media-reinforced national or cultural stereotypes are complex (Diehl & Jonas, 1991). Auto-stereotypes illustrate how a group perceives itself; hetero-stereotypes show people's views. Lack of cultural understanding might cause misconceptions that profoundly impact social conduct (Diehl & Jonas, 1991).

Cultural identity theory asserts that cultures produce self- and cultural-identities (Tajfel & Turner, 1986; Collier & Thomas, 1988). This perspective defines cultural identity as belonging to a culture and internalising its values and practices. Culture affects advertisement reactions, especially those that violate norms (Lee, 2019). Cultural traditions in China and the West allow certain advertising to portray Chinese women as meek and submissive-like (Terlutter, Diehl, Koinig, Chan, & Tsang, 2021).

The Client-Agency Dynamics in Pakistani Advertising

Successful advertising campaigns require creativity, cultural awareness, and client-agency synergy. Pakistani advertising must be culturally sensitive and effective while carefully managing client-agency dynamics. To strike this delicate balance, one needs creative freedom and knowledge of Pakistani culture and client expectations.

Clients and agencies may limit creativity due to risk aversion. Bilby et al. (2023) say consumers prefer trustworthy, safe ads, but advertising agencies may fear losing business if they take a risk. The practice, known as "clientelism," produces unappealing and quickly forgotten ads (Koslow et al., 2021).

According to Koslow et al. (2021), modest client pressure can boost agency creativity. Corporate stress can improve performance, but client arrogance can cause complacency.

We need equilibrium to control this pressure. Clients should provide sufficient resources, information, and guidance without overpowering the creative process (Vafeas, 2021). Open, honest, and trusting team relationships can inspire creativity.

Advertising in Pakistan requires understanding its culture. The incorporation of traditional symbols and beliefs, as stated by Zong et al. (2023) and Chattopadhyay et al. (2023), has the potential to improve comprehending of Pakistani culture and to assist advertising agencies in the development of creative content that is appealing to Pakistani consumers.

It isn't easy to advertise in Pakistan. Traditional thinking, excessive personnel turnover, and lacking new ideas might impede creativity (Arif et al., 2012; Saeed, 2010). A great way to boost creativity and retention of skilled personnel is to put resources into skill improvement and learning to understand and accept constructive differences.

Successful client-agency relationships require open communication, trust, and a shared commitment to

achieving creative excellence within an environment considering cultural variations. Active engagement in research and innovation and effective management of market challenges can lead to success in advertising for clients and agencies.

Methodology

This study uses a qualitative approach to find intangible factors that affect ad likeability rather than reach. The study used "elite interviews" with Pakistani advertising industry thought leaders such as brand managers, creative directors, and specialists to gain varied viewpoints on cultural, ethical, and religious variables impacting ad appeal (Braun & Clarke, 2012; Mortimer). Elite interviews with significant people illuminated the advertising scene (Dexter et al., 1970). A comprehensive understanding of brand communication was ensured by selecting interviewees based on expertise across all parties, familiarity with both domestic and international brands, relevant work experience, current senior roles, and a minimum of five years in branding management. Academics and practitioners in marketing and advertising devised and tested the interview process with advertising agency leaders. To let informants reflect, the questions were mostly open-ended (Wallendorf & Brucks, 1993). Brief profiles of informants, including brand executives, Account Directors, and Creative Directors, were created to address ethical concerns and safeguard participant confidentiality. The six Pakistani advertising professionals in the cohort exhibit an array of distinctions. Table 1 summarizes how each informant, with their specialized experience and unique perspective, sheds light on many areas of brand communication, ethics, strategy, consumer behavior, branding, and industry innovation in relation to the research objectives. The informants' unique viewpoints enhance our comprehension of the research question and provide useful information from their individual vantage points.

Table 1: Diverse Perspectives of Advertising Experts Contributing to Research Inquiry

Informant 1: Creative Director
Informant 2: Narrative Strategist
Informant 3: Strategic Communicator
Informant 4: Consumer Insight Expert
Informant 5: Branding Strategist
Informant 6: Industry Innovator

Findings

Culture and Religion Influence on Advertising

Dynamic Nature of Culture:

Informants emphasized that advertising narratives are greatly impacted by the ever-changing character of culture. Historical events, long-held ideas, and evolving social mores provide a framework that influences the development and delivery of messages. Informant 1 compares culture to a triangle of the past, present, and future, emphasizing its influence on advertising content. The historical component is important because cultural context affects even ideas like social responsibility, which guide ethics and aesthetics (Informant 1).

Kadir and Al-Aidaros (2015) found that cultural norms influence advertisement reactions. As nations and cultures change, advertisers must adjust their techniques. Brands must be relevant and engaging since "cultures change as societies do," according to an informant. Informant 4 stressed "adaptability," saying advertising must adapt to changing customer tastes. Koslow et al. (2021) emphasize that commercials must change with society to be more effective and relevant, building customer relationships.

Understanding the Audience Through Culture

Culture has a significant role in shaping consumer attitudes and beliefs, thus it's important for advertisers to understand their audience when targeting them. Informant 1 says, "it is always a delicate balance between embracing innovation and honoring tradition." Advertisements must balance innovation and tradition. Fresh ideas combined with sincerity and cultural sensitivity make a good commercial. Informant 2 says, "This method helps us create ads that people can actually understand."

Friedman (2017) and Victor (2017) say advertisers must understand market interests and cultural values to make good ads. Advertising success depends on

understanding the target audience's culture and creating consumer-friendly material that represents their beliefs. Advertising cannot connect with audiences without cultural understanding.

Balancing Innovation and Tradition

Informant 3 stressed that in order to make advertising more appealing and credible, cultural influences play a significant role in striking a balance between innovation and tradition. Developing modern ads requires an in-depth familiarity with the cultural values of the intended consumers (Schwartz & Sagiv, 1995). In order to reach various audiences and effectively impact consumer behavior, advertisers might incorporate creative concepts with culturally meaningful features. Informant 4 explained that cultural elements that speak to viewers, mirror their ideas, and make them feel connected to the ad are crucial. This method increases the product's legitimacy while simultaneously increasing its appeal. Consequently, in order to get the most out of advertising, cultural authenticity is crucial.

The Challenge of Authenticity:

The ever-changing nature of the dynamics of society emphasizes the importance of advertising adapting their methods to reflect these fundamental changes. Modern ads must reflect modern principles to engage with audiences. Advertisers must balance truthfulness and modification to match current trends and tastes (Informants 3 and 4).

Informants say targeting the fundamental message rather than sexual material or immoral language is more successful than mindlessly following Western procedures. Globalization has raised consumer expectations for high-quality local advertising that matches global standards. Thus, balancing modern influences with cultural significance is essential.

Dramatizing Western content typically backfires; thus, cultural authenticity should be prioritized.

Impact of Religion on Advertising

Creating successful commercials in Pakistan is complicated by the link between culture and religion. Informant 5 said, "the lines between religion and culture are blurred." Informant 1 called this uncertainty a "continuous war," implying that advertising creativity might be stifled by their separation. They stressed that religious principles impact cultural conventions, making creative limits difficult. Informant 3 said religious themes may work in advertising, but they need a defined methodology and ethical standards to prevent problems. Informant 4 advised against utilizing religion in commercials and instead focusing on culture to avoid alienating Islamic groups. Academic research emphasizes the role of religious and cultural backgrounds in advertising (Purnama and Safira, 2017). Advertisers may reach their target audiences by understanding religion and culture's interconnectedness.

Technology and Cultural Expression

New technology has opened up a world of possibilities for advertising to appeal to consumers' cultural sensibilities through a variety of channels, Informant 6 discussed. Modern methods must be balanced with old principles to succeed, he added further. Respecting multiple cultures and customs is as crucial as using modern advertising technology. Technological innovation and cultural awareness may help firms produce engaging ads that reach their target audience (Informant 6,3). Research shows that advertising requires new technologies and cultural knowledge (Zatar, 2015). Brand interest may increase by following cultural norms and using technology.

Evolution of Content and Cultural Sensitivity

Advertisements must adapt to complicated cultural expectations as global transformations need contact with varied people beyond looks. "Consumer expectations evolve in response to shifting cultural norms, which are in turn influenced by the dynamic changes occurring in the world," informant 2 said. Ads may win over customers' hearts and minds by catering to ethnic quirks. Modern advertising, on the other hand, tends to put an emphasis on surface-level

qualities rather than deeper meaning, drawing customers' attention away from the product's actual value and encouraging them to be more visual rather than analytical. Advertising becomes more difficult due to the abundance of visual cues. Furthermore, others worry that catering just to the needs of the present can kill creativity. Ads that are culturally sensitive are more likely to be effective because they reflect society's beliefs and values (Li & Lin, 2007; Bin Said et al., 2017).

Challenges in Advertising Innovation:

It is crucial for advertising companies to be creative while yet being attentive to cultural norms, which can be challenging in societies that are resistant to new ideas. When advertising crosses local cultural borders, it may encounter early opposition, as pointed out by Informant 3. People must learn to adapt to and appreciate one another's cultural practices if they want to be more engaged and creative. Ads may increase brand awareness and customer loyalty by speaking to consumers' emotions in a way that is meaningful to them and their culture. But you need trustworthy data to come up with fresh ad ideas. Advertising firms in Pakistan might benefit from establishing separate research sections in order to get objective opinions and create customer-friendly marketing strategies.

Client-Agency Dynamics

The imbalance of power in client-agency interactions has a major impact on the creativity of ads. According to Informant 1, a lot of clients choose tried-and-true tactics from other markets, which means they use Western advertising concepts without making any adjustments for local cultures. This power imbalance benefits clients, according to Informant 3, which limits agencies' ability to be innovative and results in advertising that don't work. When agencies put short-term client needs ahead of long-term considerations for local sensitivities, they end up playing the role of "delivery services" for deceptive advertisements, which hurts both originality and cultural relevance. According to Informant 3, in Pakistani advertising, the client-agency interaction has cultural and ethical ramifications since clients dictate the cultural and ethical boundaries for campaigns and agencies offer suggestions within those boundaries. Customers are given the freedom to choose

components that match their brand's image and the standards of society. Informant 4 stressed the importance of a well-rounded client-agency connection, saying that today's customers are savvy about global advertising and want information that is both high-quality and packed with substance. They were worried that Pakistan's distinctive advertising character may be compromised if the country merely followed Western patterns. Culturally appropriate advertising, even if it means sacrificing certain "modern" features, is important, and agencies should fight against inauthentic material and make sure their clients are aware of local cultural sensitivities. Informant 5 emphasized the need of client-agency collaboration and shared decision-making, saying that agencies should teach businesses how to run successful campaigns. A collaborative strategy that prioritizes cultural sensitivity, creativity, and ethics was suggested by Informant 6. They cautioned that budget restrictions and internal politics tend to put personal preferences ahead of cultural suitability. Advocating for creative and culturally relevant advertising techniques instead of just copying foreign material, they voiced worries about "inauthenticity" and the inability to connect with target audiences when mimicking other cultures.

The Influence of MNCs on Pakistani Advertising

The informants being the advertising experts with specialization in their respective areas collectively agreed that the Multinational Corporations (MNCs) significantly influence Pakistani advertising, impacting its quality, content, and cultural sensitivity.

Impact on Production Quality:

Most informants agreed that multinational corporations have raised the bar for production quality and content creation requirements (Informant 4). Local advertisers have had to step up their game in terms of method and quality, thanks to the advertising of multinational corporations (MNCs), each of them agreed.

Cultural Sensitivity and Ethical Considerations:

However, all informants expressed worry that MNCs care more about branding than being ethically sound and sensitive to local norms. They highlighted many famous corporations that have employed language or

advertised sensitive products that are offensive to Pakistani culture. One of the leading causes, according to Informant 3 and Informant 4, is that advertisers either don't understand or are disrespectful towards Pakistani culture. This section highlights unethical behavior and information unsuitable for a child (Informant 4).

Homogenization and Westernization:

Informants voiced their disapproval of multinational corporations' (MNCs') generic approach, which ignores the cultural nuances of local communities (Informant 1). They brought attention to the occasionally shown "abrasive westernization" in advertisements for multinational corporations (Informant 4). As a result of the multinational corporations' efforts to sell their products in a variety of regions, they have developed their primary template in western countries of origin. When these templates are used without being adapted to take into consideration the sensitivity of the local environment, the problem occurs. The fifth informant emphasized that the root of all problems is the unthinking adoption of foreign advertising concepts, which has the potential to create offence (Informant 5).

Learning and Innovation:

The informants emphasized that Pakistani advertising agencies should view this as an opportunity to learn from the creative (Informant 1) technological components of multinational corporations. On the other hand, advertising professionals in Pakistan should be aware that multinational corporations are not conscious of issues of cultural and religious sensitivity. "When it comes to ethical considerations, this can sometimes be a hindrance!" (Informant 5)

Regulation and Mitigation Strategies:

According to Informant 1, the prevention of these detrimental influences can be achieved by empowering regulatory bodies who have the responsibility to monitor and enforce compliance with cultural norms or ethical standards. PEMRA, the Pakistan Electronic Media Regulatory Authority, should enforce more stringent ethical and cultural standards. Furthermore, they recommend that advertising companies should decline customers' requests that contravene cultural norms and values.

They reached a consensus that it is necessary to offer abundant educational and training opportunities for advertising professionals. Informant 5 proposes the implementation of an awareness program to emphasize the importance of culture and religion in society and the necessity to maintain them.

While most of the informants did agree that MNCs improved production quality, they were quite worried that they were having a negative effect on cultural awareness and ethical issues in Pakistani ads. To make advertising more responsible, they call for more rules, more ethical standards, and more emphasis on cultural relevance.

Discussion & Conclusion

Advertising industry experts stress the value of culturally relevant advertising, which has a favourable effect on consumers (Zhang and Gelb, 1996; Kadir and Al-Aidaros, 2015). Ads in Pakistan should put an emphasis on cultural studies, consumer behaviour analysis, and moral business practices, according to their recommendations. Remaining culturally aware, interacting with customers, avoiding controversial topics, and providing positive role models are all important tactics. Mostafa (2011), Bin Said et al. (2017), Li and Lin (2007), and Purnama and Safira (2017) all stress the importance of cultural flexibility. Multinational corporations (MNCs) in Pakistan have contributed to culturally insensitive advertising by promoting products and services that are similar across cultures (Sarah, 2022). According to Sohail (2023) and Paracha (2015), Western media has a divisive effect on Pakistani society. The glitz and glitter of multinational corporations (MNCs) typically draws inspiration from Bollywood and the West, which local audiences are willing to embrace without much criticism (Arnold, 1982). Embracing foreign items as status symbols becomes more common due to this laxity, which in turn reduces the importance of cultural correctness (Strizhakova, Coulter, & Price, 2008).

For ads to be effective, they need to steer clear of controversial subjects, build rapport with their target audience, and be sensitive to cultural differences. Unfortunately, ads often fail to take local conditions into account since multinational corporations

(MNCs) put profit above cultural awareness. Industry insiders are calling for more research into customer habits, better communication between advertising firms and brands, and a firm resolve to do the right thing. Effective advertising requires knowledge of target cultures, in-depth analysis, and interesting copy. In order to create commercials that people can't resist, experts recommend funding advertising education programs, doing research on consumers and cultures, and using innovative content tactics. They also bring attention to the fact that the industry's worldwide competitiveness is hindered by weak leadership, poor cooperation, and inadequate finance. Leadership, collaboration, and training are crucial for advancement, according to Bilby et al. (2023). To encourage collaboration and new ideas in the advertising industry, society as a whole has to undergo a paradigm change. The advertising business in Pakistan can make a difference by working together and filling training and development funding shortfalls. This would allow them to make advertisements that speak to customers while still being ethical and culturally sensitive.

Recommendations

Key Recommendations to Improve Advertising in Pakistan

1. **Strengthen Ethical and Cultural Standards**
2. PEMRA should enforce clear ethical and cultural guidelines to ensure ads respect Pakistani values and avoid stereotypes.
3. **Promote Authentic and Culturally Sensitive Storytelling**
4. Encourage genuine, diverse, and relatable advertising that connects with audiences and builds trust.
5. **Foster Brand-Agency Collaboration**
6. Strengthen partnerships to produce creative, consistent, and culturally relevant campaigns.
7. **Use Data-Driven Insights**
8. Apply audience analytics to design targeted, respectful, and engaging advertisements.
9. **Encourage Innovation and Creativity**
10. Support new formats, fresh ideas, and responsible experimentation to keep Pakistan's advertising industry competitive and dynamic.

Limitations of the Study

The study may be restricted in generalisability and interpretation. Few advertising experts are interviewed in "elite interviews" for the research. This technique collects valuable data but may miss Pakistani advertising stakeholders like consumers. Although the informants are knowledgeable, the sample is biased since it only represents a small portion of the advertising industry's elite. They may see things differently than smaller companies or those outside advertising hubs. The findings may only relate to Pakistani advertising, not other cultures. The study focuses the perspectives of informants regarding the characteristics of advertisements. It doesn't survey or experiment, so it may overlook viewers' preconceptions or commercial responses.

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